

**Corporate Governance Mechanisms and Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG)
Disclosure in Nigeria**

Bernice Ngozi OKOHDONATUS

Department of Accounting,
Faculty of Management Sciences,
University of Benin, Benin City.
bernicedo1okoh2@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and environmental, social, and governance (ESG) disclosure among non-financial firms in Nigeria. The study examined whether board size, board independence, board gender diversity, and audit committee size influence ESG disclosure practices using a balanced panel of 89 Nigerian listed firms over the period 2015 to 2024. ESG disclosure was measured using a multi-dimensional index to capture environmental, human capital, product responsibility, and community engagement disclosures. Panel regression techniques were employed for data analysis. The results indicated that board size is significantly and negatively associated with ESG disclosure, while board gender diversity exhibits a positive and statistically significant relationship. In contrast, board independence and audit committee size do not significantly influence ESG disclosure. The study concludes that corporate governance mechanisms influence ESG disclosure, but their effectiveness varies across governance attributes. The study recommends amongst others that environmental expertise should be integrated into criteria for board appointments.

Keywords: ESG disclosure; Corporate governance; Board gender diversity; Environmental accountability; Emerging economies

JEL Classification: G34, M14, M41

1. Introduction

Climate change, environmental degradation, and social inequalities have intensified global calls for greater corporate accountability and sustainable production practices. Firms are increasingly expected to disclose transparent and decision-useful ESG information to demonstrate their commitment to environmental stewardship, social responsibility, and sound governance (ISSB, 2023; Khan et al., 2021). ESG disclosure has therefore become a central mechanism through which firms communicate their contribution to sustainable development. ESG reporting has emerged as a central pillar of corporate accountability, driven by increasing global concern over climate change, social inequality, ethical governance, sustainable value creation, performance management and measurement. Institutional investors, regulators, and international standard-

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setting bodies now demand firms to provide transparent and decision-useful ESG disclosures alongside traditional financial reporting (IFRS Foundation, 2023; KPMG, 2024).

Despite growing regulatory and stakeholder pressure, ESG disclosure practices remain uneven across jurisdictions, particularly in emerging economies where institutional enforcement is weak and sustainability reporting is largely voluntary (Adegbite et al., 2023; Velte, 2023). In this contexts, internal governance mechanisms, especially board structures, play a critical role in shaping firms' environmental accountability and ESG disclosure practices by influencing board oversight, managerial accountability, strong management system, measurement and strategic orientation toward sustainability. Effective governance structures are increasingly viewed as essential for ensuring credible ESG reporting, reducing information asymmetry, and aligning corporate actions with stakeholder and societal expectations (García-Sánchez & Martínez-Ferrero, 2023; Velte, 2024).

While prior studies have examined governance, ESG relationships, evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa remains limited and often focused on CSR expenditure rather than disclosure quality (Fatima et al., 2023). This study addresses the gap by investigating how corporate governance mechanisms influence ESG disclosure among Nigerian non-financial firms, with specific emphasis on environmental transparency and sustainability. Globally, ESG disclosure has transitioned from a predominantly voluntary practice to a quasi-mandatory reporting regime, particularly following the establishment of the International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) and the growing adoption of IFRS S1 and S2 standards (IFRS Foundation, 2023). These developments underscore the importance of board-level governance in ensuring consistent, reliable, and comparable ESG disclosures across jurisdictions.

Board characteristics, such as board size, board independence, gender diversity, and audit committee structure, have been identified as key governance mechanisms influencing ESG disclosure quality. Prior studies suggest that well-structured and diverse boards enhance performance management, monitoring effectiveness, promote ethical decision-making, and strengthen firms' sustainability orientation (Kyaw et al., 2023; Lagasio & Cucari, 2019; Velte, 2024). In particular, board gender diversity has gained prominence in ESG discourse, with empirical evidence linking female representation on boards to enhanced environmental and social transparency. Despite these developments, empirical evidence on the governance and ESG disclosure nexus in sub-Saharan Africa remains fragmented.

The study makes three contributions. First, it provides emerging-market evidence on board-level drivers of ESG disclosure. Second, it introduces a multi-dimensional ESG disclosure index aligned with sustainability reporting frameworks. Third, it offers policy-relevant and performance management insights for strengthening environmental governance practices. In emerging economy like Nigeria, ESG disclosure is particularly salient due to persistent environmental degradation, governance weaknesses, and rising stakeholder activism. However, looking at the Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance (NCCG, 2018) which laid emphasizes on board accountability, diversity,

audit effectiveness, and sustainability oversight, aligning Nigeria with global governance reforms. Nevertheless, ESG disclosures remains uneven, often emphasizing social philanthropy while providing limited environmental and governance-related information (Adegbite et al., 2023; Owusu et al., 2024).

The remaining of the study is structured thus: section 2 covers the literature review and theoretical framework; section 3 covers the methodology; section 4 Data presentation, interpretation, analysis, result and discussion, and policy implications of findings; and section 5 gives the conclusion and recommendations.

2. Literature Review and Hypotheses Formulation

2.1. Concept of ESG disclosure

ESG disclosure enhances environmental accountability by improving transparency on firms' resource use, emissions, waste management, and social impacts, existing literature emphasizes that disclosure complements operational sustainability by enabling monitoring, benchmarking, and stakeholder engagement (Cho et al., 2021; García-Sánchez et al., 2020). ESG disclosure has become a cornerstone of contemporary corporate reporting, reflecting heightened global concern over climate risk, carbon disclosure, social inequality, ethical governance, and long-term value creation. ESG disclosure extends beyond traditional financial reporting by providing non-financial information relevant to investors, regulators, and broader stakeholders in assessing corporate sustainability performance (García-Sánchez & Martínez-Ferrero, 2023; Velte, 2024).

Recent global regulatory developments, most notably the establishment of the International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) and the introduction of IFRS S1 and S2, have accelerated the institutionalization of ESG disclosure within the global space. These developments emphasize governance oversight, risk management, and board accountability as critical enablers of high-quality ESG reporting (IFRS Foundation, 2023). Consequently, corporate governance mechanisms are increasingly viewed as central determinants of the credibility, consistency, and depth of ESG disclosure. However, firms in emerging economies often prioritize social disclosures over environmental reporting, reflecting legitimacy-seeking behaviour, hence ignoring critical theory rather than substantive sustainability transformation (Hahn & Kühnen, 2023).

2.2. Corporate governance mechanisms and ESG disclosure

2.2.1. Board size and ESG disclosure

Board size influences the breadth of expertise, monitoring capacity, and strategic oversight available to firms. Larger boards may enhance ESG disclosure by incorporating diverse knowledge and stakeholder perspectives. However, excessively large boards may suffer from coordination inefficiencies, diluting accountability (Velte, 2024). Smaller boards are argued to be more effective in sustainability oversight due to improved coordination and faster decision-making (Velte, 2023). Conversely, larger boards may experience free-rider problems and diluted accountability. Empirical evidence remains mixed. While several studies report a positive association between board size and ESG disclosure quality (Kyaw et al., 2023), others document insignificant or

negative effects, particularly in emerging markets where board effectiveness may be constrained by institutional weaknesses (Ofoegbu et al., 2023). These inconsistencies suggest that the board size, ESG disclosure relationship is context-specific. Consequently, we hypothesize that board size is significantly associated with ESG disclosure (H1).

2.2.2 Board independence and ESG disclosure

Board independence is widely regarded as a cornerstone of effective corporate governance. Independent directors are expected to enhance oversight, reduce agency conflicts, and promote transparent ESG disclosure. Recent studies in developed economies largely support a positive association between board independence and ESG reporting quality (García-Sánchez & Martínez-Ferrero, 2023). However, evidence from emerging markets is less conclusive. Weak enforcement, symbolic independence, and concentrated ownership structures may undermine the effectiveness of independent directors in influencing ESG disclosure practices (Owusu et al., 2024). This raises concerns about the substantive role of independence in institutional environments characterized by governance fragility. Independent directors are expected to enhance monitoring and transparency; however, evidence from emerging economies suggests independence may be symbolic without ESG expertise or enforcement capacity (Adegbite et al., 2023). Nevertheless, we hypothesize that board independence is significantly associated with ESG disclosure (H2).

2.2.3 Board gender diversity and ESG disclosure

Board gender diversity has emerged as a critical governance mechanism in ESG discourse. Female directors are often associated with higher ethical sensitivity, stakeholder orientation, and long-term sustainability focus. Empirical evidence increasingly supports a positive relationship between board gender diversity and ESG disclosure quality (Kyaw et al., 2023; Rao & Tilt, 2024). Nevertheless, the effectiveness of gender diversity may be constrained by tokenism, cultural barriers, and limited decision-making influence in some emerging economies. As such, the presence of women on boards does not automatically translate into enhanced ESG disclosure without substantive participation. Female directors are associated with ethical sensitivity, stakeholder orientation, and long-term sustainability focus, making gender-diverse boards more conducive to ESG transparency (Rao & Tilt, 2021; Velte, 2023). Therefore, we hypothesize that board gender diversity is significantly associated with ESG disclosure (H3).

2.2.4 Audit committee size and ESG disclosure

Audit committees play a vital role in ensuring the integrity of corporate reporting systems. Larger and more effective audit committees are found to enhance internal controls, risk management, and assurance processes, are increasingly relevant for ESG disclosure credibility (Velte, 2024). Although research on audit committee characteristics and ESG disclosure remains limited, emerging evidence suggests that audit committees can positively influence ESG transparency by strengthening oversight of non-financial reporting (Ofoegbu et al., 2023). However, findings remain inconclusive, particularly in developing economies. Audit committee size may enhance disclosure quality, but their traditional focus on financial reporting may limit their influence on

ESG issues. Consequently, we hypothesize that audit committee size is significantly associated with ESG disclosure (H4).

2.2.5 ESG disclosure evidence from Nigeria

Despite increasing global ESG pressures, firms in emerging economies continue to exhibit relatively low ESG disclosure quality. In Nigeria, ESG reporting remains largely voluntary, fragmented, and skewed toward narrative social disclosures, with limited emphasis on environmental risk metrics and governance structures (Adebite & Nakajima, 2024; Uwuigbe et al., 2023). The Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance (2018) emphasizes board accountability, diversity, and audit effectiveness. However, implementation gaps and weak enforcement persist, limiting the effectiveness of governance mechanisms in driving substantive ESG disclosure. Existing studies report mixed findings and often examine governance attributes in isolation, leaving the combined effects of board characteristics underexplored.

Empirical evidence from Nigeria indicates a gradual but uneven improvement in ESG disclosure practices. Studies employing ESG disclosure indices and content analysis reveal that firms increasingly emphasize environmental and economic disclosures, while social and governance components remain relatively underdeveloped (Anaeye et al., 2025; Busari & Adebayibi, 2025). This imbalance reflects firms' strategic focus on disclosures perceived as more value-relevant to capital markets. Sector-specific studies further highlight disclosure heterogeneity. In the oil and gas sector, ESG disclosure intensity has increased in response to stakeholder pressure and international scrutiny. However, environmental disclosure quality remains inconsistent, often driven by legitimacy concerns rather than substantive environmental performance (Ogriki & Boubai, 2025). Similar patterns are observed in manufacturing and consumer goods firms, where disclosure is frequently compliance-oriented rather than strategically embedded (Ogbu et al., 2025). Overall, while ESG reporting has expanded in scope following regulatory interventions by the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX), empirical findings suggest that depth, credibility, and integration of ESG disclosures remain limited.

Bello and Ngerebo (2025) report that board gender diversity does not exert a statistically significant effect on ESG transparency among Nigerian deposit money banks, suggesting that symbolic representation without substantive decision-making power may not enhance disclosure quality. Conversely, broader governance attributes, including board independence and institutional ownership, have been found to positively influence environmental and sustainability disclosures in emerging African markets including Nigeria (Nnedu et al., 2025). Firm size and profitability also emerge as consistent drivers, with larger firms exhibiting higher ESG disclosure levels due to greater public visibility and stakeholder pressure (Anaeye et al., 2025). These findings align with legitimacy theory and stakeholder theory, which posit that firms disclose ESG information to maintain social acceptance and manage stakeholder relationships within weak institutional environments.

Ogbu et al. (2025) find that environmental disclosure negatively affects profitability in manufacturing firms, potentially due to high compliance and implementation costs. Similarly, studies on consumer goods firms under mandatory sustainability disclosure regimes reveal that while environmental disclosure enhances return on assets (ROA), social disclosure exerts a negative effect, and governance disclosure remains insignificant (Nnedu et al., 2025). In the oil and gas sector, social and governance disclosures demonstrate stronger performance relevance than environmental disclosure, reflecting sector-specific stakeholder expectations and regulatory exposure (Ogriki & Boubai, 2025).

2.3 Theoretical perspectives underpinning ESG disclosure

The agency theory was propounded and developed by Michael C. Jensen and William H. Meckling in 1976. Agency theory posits that ESG disclosure reduces information asymmetry between managers and shareholders by enhancing transparency and monitoring effectiveness. Board structures and audit committees serve as internal governance mechanisms that constrain opportunistic behaviour and improve disclosure quality (Velte, 2024). Freeman et al. (2023) found stakeholder theory as broaden to corporate accountability beyond shareholders to include employees, communities, regulators, and the environment. ESG disclosure is viewed as a strategic communication tool through which firms respond to stakeholder demands for sustainability and ethical conduct (Freeman et al., 2023).

Legitimacy theory was propounded by John Dowling and Jeffrey Pfeffer. in the year 1975. The theory suggests that firms disclose ESG information to align with societal norms and expectations, thereby maintaining social approval and organizational survival. In emerging economies, ESG disclosure often functions as a legitimacy-seeking mechanism, particularly in environmentally sensitive industries (Deegan, 2023).

Critical theory was propounded by Max Horkheimer in the year 1937 and it explains that corporate governance mechanisms shape ESG disclosure by challenging power imbalances and promoting transparency. Strong boards, independent directors, and audit committees can pressure management to disclose ESG information that reflects broader stakeholder interests rather than narrow shareholder goals so doing will enhances accountability and reduces information asymmetry (Adams, 2022; Gray et al., 2023). Thus, governance structures act as instruments for advancing social justice and ethical reporting within ESG frameworks. Together, these theories provide a robust explanatory framework for examining how governance mechanisms shape ESG disclosure practices.

Furthermore, Critical theory provides a powerful lens for understanding the real challenges of performance management and accountability in the ESG disclosure, it also reveals that governance failures are not merely technical but deeply rooted in power structures, institutional weaknesses, and political dynamics. For countries like Nigeria, it offers a more realistic explanation of why reforms succeed or fail and provides a foundation for more inclusive, transparent, and effective ESG disclosure performance system and accountability are central to effective governance. When

supported by strong legal systems and institutional frameworks, they enhance transparency, efficiency, and service delivery in sustainable economy. (Pérez-Durán, 2023; Rodríguez Bolívar, 2026).

3. Methodology

3.1. Research design and sampling

This study adopts a longitudinal ex post facto research design using panel data from 89 non-financial firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group between 2015 and 2024, yielding 534 firm-year observations to examine the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and ESG disclosure practices among listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. This design is appropriate for sustainability and governance research relying on archival data and non-manipulable firm characteristics (Baltagi, 2021; Wooldridge, 2019).

The sample period spans 2015-2024, corresponding to the post-IFRS adoption era in Nigeria, a period associated with enhanced disclosure requirements and improved transparency in non-financial reporting. The population consists of 151 firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as at December 31, 2024. Financial institutions were excluded due to their unique regulatory frameworks and ESG disclosure obligations. After excluding firms with incomplete data, the final sample comprises 89 non-financial firms, yielding 534 firm-year observations. This sample represents over 70% of the non-financial sector, ensuring sufficient cross-sectional and temporal coverage.

3.2. Data sources and ESG disclosure measurement

Data were obtained from audited annual reports and sustainability-related disclosures. ESG disclosure data were collected using manual content analysis, a widely accepted approach in ESG and sustainability research due to the qualitative and narrative nature of such disclosures (Cho et al., 2021; Hahn & Kuhnen, 2023). ESG disclosure is measured using an unweighted index capturing four dimensions: environmental, human capital, product responsibility, and community engagement. While this index primarily focuses on the environmental and social (E & S) dimension of ESG, the governance aspect is implicitly captured through management's strategic transparency in stakeholder reporting. Content analysis of annual reports was conducted following established ESG disclosure methodologies (Cormier et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2021).

The ESGD score is computed as the ratio of items disclosed by firm i in year t to the maximum possible disclosure items. This approach aligns with recent ESG measurement frameworks used in sustainability and accounting literature (Cormier et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2021).

3.3. Corporate governance variables

Corporate governance mechanisms are operationalized as follows:

Board Size (BS): total number of directors on the board;

Board Independence (BIND): proportion of independent non-executive directors;

Board Gender Diversity (BGED): proportion of female directors;

Audit Committee Size (AUDCS): it is measured as the total number of members serving on the audit committee during the financial year;

Firm Size (FSIZE): natural logarithm of total assets (control variable)

3.4. Model specification and estimation

The baseline panel regression model is specified as:

$$ESGD_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BS_{it} + \beta_2 BIND_{it} + \beta_3 BGED_{it} + \beta_4 AUDCS_{it} + \beta_5 FSIZE_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots (1)$$

Pooled OLS, fixed effects, and random effects models were estimated in this study. Panel estimation was utilized to control for unobserved firm-specific heterogeneity and increase efficiency (Baltagi, 2021). Based on the Hausman test, the random-effects model was selected as the most suitable, and heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors were incorporated.

To validate the robustness of the econometric model, a series of post-estimation diagnostic tests were conducted. Multicollinearity was evaluated using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). Furthermore, the Breusch–Godfrey test checked for serial correlation, the Breusch–Pagan–Godfrey test detected heteroskedasticity, and the Ramsey regression specification error test (RESET) verified the functional form. To address the presence of serial correlation, heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors were employed for all coefficient estimates.

The analytical framework in Figure 1 depicts schematic representation of the causal relations with the dependent variable ESG and the independent variables (board size, board independence, board gender diversity, audit committee size).

Figure 1. Analytical Framework

Source: Author's Compilation (2025)

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Descriptive analysis

The mean ESG disclosure score of 0.29 indicates a relatively low level of ESG transparency, consistent with evidence from emerging economies where sustainability reporting remains largely voluntary (Adegbite et al., 2023; Ntim & Soobaroyen, 2019).

Table 1 Results of the Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

	ESGD	BS	BIND	BGED	AUDCS	FSIZE
Mean	0.288190	8.844569	0.606386	0.112990	5.477528	6.965140
Median	0.281752	8.000000	0.625000	0.100000	6.000000	6.911558
Maximum	0.572190	19.000000	0.900000	0.670000	9.000000	9.229032
Minimum	0.040000	3.000000	0.250000	0.000000	0.000000	4.758056
Std. Dev.	0.096852	2.776915	0.120930	0.122765	1.151905	0.811782
Skewness	0.204378	0.736625	-0.305534	1.307760	-1.378936	0.062271
Kurtosis	2.688312	3.676886	2.830198	5.706567	7.325361	3.117204
Jarque-Bera	5.879130	58.48719	8.949750	315.2035	585.5002	0.650755
Probability	0.052889	0.000000	0.011392	0.000000	0.000000	0.722255
Sum	153.8936	4723.000	323.8101	60.33677	2925.000	3719.385
Sum Sq. Dev.	4.999734	4110.099	7.794653	8.033008	707.2303	351.2415
Observations	534	534	534	534	534	534

Source: Researchers Computation (E-views 8) 2025

The result of the descriptive statistics as shown in table 1 reveals a mean Environmental Social Governance disclosure (ESGD) of 0.29 (29%). The result also reveals a mean board size of 8.84, an indication that the sampled firms have an average of approximately 9 directors on their board, board independence of about 60.64%, board gender of 11.30%, audit committee size of 5.48 approximately 6 directors on the audit committee and firm size of 6.97. The maximum value of the dependent variable ESGD is 0.57 with a minimum value of 0.04, evidence that all the sampled companies disclosed at least an item of ESG in their annual report. For the independent variables, board size has a maximum value of 19 and a minimum of 3 directors. The maximum for board independence is 0.90 and the minimum is 0.25. Board gender diversity which is an indication of the ratio of female directors to total directors has a maximum of 0.67 and a minimum of 0.00. the audit committee size has a maximum of 9 directors and a minimum of 0. Lastly for the control variable, firm size which is measured using the logarithm of total assets had a maximum value of 9.23 and a minimum value of 4.76. Figure 2 reports the percentage level of each of the categories.

4.2. Components descriptive statistics

The extent to which the sampled companies disclosed the ESG factor items in respect to the four (4) sub-categories adapted from Nour et al. (2020) are presented in Table 2:

Table 2: Descriptive statistics for the item of ESG Disclosure index

s/n	Sub-Categories	Average Disclosure	% of Disclosure	Rank
1.	Environment/Natural Resources	0.170	15%	4 th
2.	Human Resources (Employees)	0.314	27%	2 nd
3.	Product or Service Contributions	0.297	26%	3 rd
4.	Community Involvement	0.371	32%	1 st
Overall average disclosure		0.288	100%	

Source: Researchers Compilation, 2025

Figure 2 Graphical Representation of the Percentage of ESG Disclosures

Figure 3 Histogram Normality Test

Source: Researchers Computation, 2025

The result of the histogram normality test revealed a mean Jarque-Bera test of 4.97 and a probability value of 0.08. The result of the test suggests a normally distributed regression variable. The mean positive kurtosis of 2.73 revealed a positive kurtosis short of 3.00 which signifies a kurtosis below the 3.00 benchmark. The mean positive skewness of 0.19 means rightward skewed regression variables. The average standard deviation of 0.09 shows that the deviation from the mean of the regression variables is relatively small.

4.3. Correlation analysis

Table 3 Correlation Analysis

	ESGD	BS	BIND	BGED	AUDCS	FSIZE
ESGD	1.000000					
BS	-0.203129	1.000000				
BIND	-0.073852	0.222317	1.000000			
BGED	0.093216	0.070765	0.082988	1.000000		
AUDCS	-0.117884	0.418571	0.138041	0.059079	1.000000	
FSIZE	-0.159173	0.507125	0.110875	0.052702	0.415011	1.000000

Source: Researchers Computation, 2025

The result of the correlation coefficient revealed mixed coefficients of both positive and negative values. The correlation coefficient between the dependent variable of environmental social governance disclosure and the independent variables of board size, board independence, audit committee size and firm size were negative with values of -0.20, -0.07, -0.12 and -0.16. The correlation coefficients between the dependent variable of corporate social responsibility disclosure and the independent variable of board gender were positive with value of 0.09. The

correlation coefficients did not pose any problem of multicollinearity as the results of correlation coefficients are relatively small. The highest value of correlation coefficient is between board size and firm size with values of 0.51. The result of the variance inflation factor is a further confirmation of the absence of the problem of multicollinearity in the regression variables.

4.4. Diagnostic tests

4.4.1. Test for Multicollinearity

Table 4 Variance Inflation Factors :

Variable	Coefficient		Centered VIF
	Uncentered VIF	Variance	
C	98.58686	0.001645	NA
BS	16.68643	3.24E-06	1.494734
BIND	27.75864	0.001211	1.059860
BGED	1.868797	0.001121	1.010881
AUDCS	30.84754	1.64E-05	1.304102
FSIZE	107.9190	3.66E-05	1.443624

Source: Researchers computation (2025)

The result of the variance inflation factor revealed relatively low centered variance inflation factors of 1.49 for board size; 1.06 for board independence; 1.01 for board gender; 1.30 for audit committee size and 1.44 for firm size. The result is a further confirmation of the results of the correlation analysis in table 4.2

4.4.2 Test for Serial Correlation

Table 5 Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:

F-statistic	82.88620 Prob. F(2,526)	0.0000
Obs*R-squared	127.9647 Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.0000

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

The result of the Breusch-Godfrey test of serial correlation indicates the presence of serial correlation in the variables of regression. The F-statistic of 23.68 and the probability value of 0.0000 indicate that the null hypothesis of no serial correlation is rejected, hence we accept the alternate hypothesis of serially correlated variables. This error was addressed using the White cross-section standard errors & covariance

4.4.3. Test for Heteroskedasticity

Table 6 Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	0.929456	Prob. F(5,528)	0.4614
Obs*R-squared	4.659082	Prob. Chi-Square(5)	0.4589
Scaled explained SS	3.934538	Prob. Chi-Square(5)	0.5589

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

The test of heteroskedasticity was conducted using the Breusch-Pagan Godfrey test. The result of the test reported an F-statistic of 0.93 and an insignificant probability value of 0.46. The result of the test accepts the null hypothesis of homoscedastic residuals.

4.4.4 Test for model specification

Table 7. Result of the Ramsey Reset Test

	Value	Df	Probability
t-statistic	1.457197	527	0.1457
F-statistic	2.123422	(1, 527)	0.1457
Likelihood ratio	2.147304	1	0.1428

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

Furthermore, Ramsey reset test of model specification was adopted to test the accuracy of the regression model. The result of the test reported an F-statistic of 2.12 and an insignificant probability value of 0.15. The result of the test accepts the null hypothesis of properly specified model.

4.5. Regression Analysis

Table 8 Results of the Regression Analyses

VARIABLE	POOLED	FIXED EFFECT	RANDOM EFFECT
C	0.42 (0.00)	0.49 (0.00)	0.42 (0.00)
BS	-0.00 (0.00)	-0.01 (0.02)	-0.01 (0.00)
BIND	-0.03 (0.12)	-0.03 (0.37)	-0.03 (0.19)
BGED	0.09 (0.00)	0.02 (0.73)	0.06 (0.03)
AUDCS	-0.00 (0.17)	-0.00 (0.64)	-0.00 (0.48)
FSIZE	-0.01 (0.01)	-0.02 (0.51)	-0.01 (0.20)
R-squared	0.06	0.57	0.03
Adjusted R-squared	0.05	0.48	0.02
F-statistic	6.65	6.32	2.97
Prob(F-statistic)	0.00	0.00	0.01
Durbin-Watson Stat	1.06	2.11	1.79
Redundant Fixed Effects Test		5.98 (0.00)	
Hausman		0.00 (1.00)	
Observations	534	534	534

Source: Researchers Computation (E-views) 2025.

The coefficient values are reported (probability values are in parenthesis)

The result of the regression analysis presented in Table 8 shows the pooled, random effect and fixed effect regression analysis. The result of the redundant fixed effect with F-statistic value of 5.98 and probability value of 0.0000 shows the pooled OLS is not adequate hence we proceed to

test between fixed and random effects model. The result of the Hausman Test with a probability value of 1.00 and a Chi-sq value of 0.00 shows preference for the random effect model. The result of the Hausman Test accepts the null hypothesis of equality of coefficients between the random and fixed effect model. The coefficient of multiple correlation of the pooled regression result is 0.06 with an adjusted R-square of 0.05. The coefficient of multiple correlation of the fixed effects model is 0.57 with an adjusted R-square of 0.48. The random effect model has a coefficient of multiple correlation of 0.03 with an adjusted R-square of 0.02. The adjusted R-square value of 0.02 shows that about 2% of the systematic cross-sectional variation of the dependent variable of corporate social responsibility disclosure is accounted for by the independent variables of board size, board independence, board gender, audit committee size and firm size. The F-statistic value of 2.97 obtained from the random effect model and the significant probability value of 0.01 shows that a significant linear relationship exists between the dependent variable and the independent variables. Board size exhibits a significant negative relationship with ESG disclosure, while board gender diversity shows a positive and significant association. Board independence and audit committee size are insignificant.

4.6. Discussion of Findings

The findings suggest that there is a negative significant relationship between board size and ESG disclosure. This implies that, in the context of this study, companies with larger boards are associated with lower ESG disclosures. Gender-diverse boards play a critical role in advancing environmental accountability, while large boards hinder effective ESG oversight. Persistent under-reporting of environmental issues raises concerns for climate governance.

The negative association between board size and ESG disclosure suggests that larger boards may suffer from coordination inefficiencies and slower decision-making, limiting their effectiveness in advancing sustainability transparency. This finding aligns with behavioral governance perspectives and recent ESG governance evidence from emerging markets (García-Sánchez et al., 2020; Velte, 2023). The non-significant role of board independence indicates that formal independence alone may be insufficient to enhance ESG disclosure in weak institutional environments, where independent directors often lack ESG-specific expertise or enforcement power (Adegbite et al., 2023).

In contrast, board gender diversity emerges as a key driver of ESG disclosure, supporting stakeholder and legitimacy theories. Female directors are associated with enhanced ethical sensitivity, stakeholder engagement, and long-term sustainability orientation (Post & Byron, 2015; Rao & Tilt, 2021; Velte, 2023). The insignificance of audit committee size suggests that ESG oversight remains outside the traditional financial reporting mandate of audit committees in Nigeria, underscoring the need for clearer ESG governance responsibilities.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

This study concludes that ESG disclosure quality is significantly influenced by selected board governance characteristics, like board size showing statistically significant and negative impact. Strengthening board diversity and optimizing board size can enhance environmental transparency and support objectives in emerging economies. This study also provides robust evidence that corporate governance mechanisms influence ESG disclosure, but their effectiveness varies across governance attributes. Globally, their effectiveness remains constrained by structural, institutional, and political challenges. In other to addressing these issues, particularly in Nigeria, requires strengthening data systems, building behavioral patterns through human capacity and management control system that is benchmarked through the creation of business model theory that will drive strict policy implementation and sanctions, improving KPI design, and reinforcing accountability mechanisms to ensure that performance management achieves its intended outcomes in ESG disclosure sustainability.

Board gender diversity and board size emerge as the most influential governance drivers of ESG transparency among Nigerian non-financial firms. The findings highlight persistent imbalances in ESG disclosure, with limited environmental accountability, posing challenges for sustainable development and climate governance in emerging economies. Empirical evidence on Critical Theory support for Accountability systems often fail due to institutional and political constraints, governance outcomes depend on alignment between institutional design and performance systems, ESG disclosure are shaped by power dynamics and political context, research shows need for broader accountability beyond compliance, governance mechanisms are influenced by politics, not just efficiency, while accountability mechanisms may be weak despite formal structures, legal systems alone cannot ensure transparency and power dynamics shape ESG disclosure performance and measurement outcomes.

5.2 Policy implications and Recommendations

1. Embed gender diversity targets in governance codes, Mandate board-level ESG oversight, integrate environmental expertise into board appointments, Strengthen ESG reporting enforcement mechanisms.
2. Firms should maintain moderate board sizes to enhance decision efficiency and ESG oversight
3. Gender diversity targets should be explicitly embedded in corporate governance codes
4. ESG competence, rather than formal independence alone, should guide board appointments
5. Audit committees should be formally mandated to oversee ESG reporting and assurance.

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